

Deliverable 7.2

Interim Impact Assessment Report

Due date of deliverable: 31/01/2024

Actual submission date: 08/02/2024

Start date of project: 01/02/2022 Duration (36 Months)

Dissemination Level: Public ✓

DELIVERABLE

Work Package	WP7 Evaluation and Impact Assessment
Deliverable	D7.2 Interim Impact Assessment Report
Document Name	D7.2: Interim Impact Assessment Report
Due Date	M24: 31 January 2024
Submission Date	M24: 31 January 2024
Dissemination Level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> P – Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO – Confidential
Deliverable Leads	ZSI, UCT–Open AIR
Authors	Chris Armstrong (Chris.Armstrong@wits.ac.za), Teresa Schaefer (schaefer@zsi.at), Claudia Magdalena Fabian (fabian@zsi.at)
Contributors	Barbara Kieslinger (kieslinger@zsi.at), Anna Sera Lowe (anna@manufacturingchange.org), Fabienne Kirchhof (f.kirchhof@greentec-capital.com), Josef Agyina (joseph@africamakerspace.net), Thomas Hervé Mboa Nkoudou (thomasmboa@gmail.com), Jessica Nguema (jessica.nguema@internetofproduction.org), Barbara Schack (barbara.schack@internetofproduction.org), Guenda Dalcin (guenda@fablabbcn.org), Kirstin Wiedow (kirstin@globalinnovationgathering.org), Antonio Anaya (antonio.anaya@internetofproduction.org), Sarah Hutton (sarah.hutton@internetofproduction.org)
Point of Contact	Barbara Kieslinger (kieslinger@zsi.at)
Reviewers	Fabienne Kirchof (f.kirchhof@greentec-capital.com), Stephane Fadanka (stephanefadanka@gmail.com)
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Plan <input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Working <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final <input type="checkbox"/> Approved
Abstract (for public dissemination)	This document describes the Interim Impact Assessment Report for the mAkE project
Keywords	evaluation, impact assessment

The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the mAKE project consortium under EC grant agreement number 101016858 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Document History

Version	Date	Comment
001	14.11.2023	First structure and outline
002	17.01.2024	Main content added to all chapters by WP leaders
003	22.01.2024	WP content harmonised, and summary sections added
004	24.01.2024	Peer review
005	27.01.2024	Integration of peer review comments
1.00	08.02.2024	Final editing and submission

List of Figures

Figure 1: Collected expectations and brainstorming of project legacy during the Kickoff Meeting	13
Figure 2: Maker Passport – record form for users	32
Figure 3: Development steps of the Maker Passport	33
Figure 4: Maker Passport – simplified record form for users.....	36
Figure 5: Map at https://map.internetofproduction.org/makeafricaeu.html	38
Figure 6: Data collection tool at https://map.internetofproduction.org/data-submission/index.html	40
Figure 7: Open-Know-Where DevOps infrastructure diagram (Rev.O).....	42

List of Abbreviations

AMN	Africa Makerspace Network
AMG	Africa Makerspace Gathering
AOSH	Africa Open Science Hardware
API	application programming interface
APSOHA	Association pour la Promotion de la Science Ouverte en Haïti et en Afrique
B2B	business-to-business
CA	Consortium Agreement
CNC	computer numerical control
CO	confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	digital object identifier
DoW	Description of Work
DSI	digital social innovation
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FGD	focus group discussion

F2F	founder-to-founder
GA	Grant Agreement
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering
GDIW	Ghana Digital Innovation Week
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation (EU)
GreenTec	GreenTec Capital Africa Foundation
H2020	Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union
IAAC	Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia
IMA	Innovative Manufacturing in Africa
IOP Alliance	Internet of Production Alliance
IPRs	intellectual property rights
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	key performance indicator
MAB	mAKE Advisory Board
MiR	Makers-in-Residency
MOOC	massive open online course
NGO	non-governmental organisation
NoSQL	not only SQL (see "SQL")
OCBM	Open Catalogue of Business Models
OERs	open educational resources

OKW	Open Know-Where
Open AIR	Open African Innovation Research
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
OSHWA	Open Source Hardware Association
PMB	Project Management Board
PSS	People and Skills Specification
PU	public
RE	restricted
R&I	Research & Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals (UN)
SMEs	small and medium-sized enterprises
SQL	structured query language
RISA	Research and Innovation Systems for Africa
STEM	science, technology, engineering and mathematics
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
UCT	University of Cape Town
UNHCR	UN Refugee Agency
WP	work package
Y1	project year one
Y2	project year two

Y3	project year three
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation

Table of contents

Executive summary	10
1. Introduction.....	12
2. Vision	12
3. Venture building and business models (WP1)	14
3.1 Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM)	14
3.1.1 OCBM mentoring programme.....	15
3.1.2 First lessons learnt.....	16
3.1.3 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3.....	17
3.2 Venture Building and Business Development programme.....	18
3.2.1 First lessons learnt.....	19
3.2.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3.....	21
3.3 Makers-in-Residency (MiR) programme.....	21
3.3.1 First lessons learnt.....	22
3.3.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3.....	23
4. Hub ecosystem and policy frameworks (WP2).....	23
4.1 First lessons learnt.....	26
4.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3	27
5. Open education, skill development and capacity building (WP3)	27
5.1 Open Makerspace Toolkit and training of trainers	27
5.1.1 First lessons learnt.....	29
5.1.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3.....	30
6. Distributed manufacturing network (WP4).....	31
6.1 People and Skills Specification (PSS) and Maker Passport prototype	31
6.1.1 People and Skills Specification (PSS): Overview	31
6.1.2 Maker Passport for mutual skills recognition: Overview	31
6.1.3 Evidence-informed development	32
6.1.4 First lessons learnt.....	35
6.1.5 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3.....	36
6.2 Map of Machinery.....	37
6.2.1 First lessons learnt.....	41

6.2.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3.....	44
6.3 Digital contracting system for distributed manufacturing.....	45
6.3.1 First lessons learnt.....	46
6.3.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3.....	47
7. Communication, dissemination and outreach (WP5).....	48
7.1 First lessons learnt.....	49
7.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3	49
8. Community engagement and sustainability (WP6).....	49
8.1 First lessons learnt.....	52
8.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3	53
9. Overview of mAke indicator framework at end of Y2 and summary of lessons learnt.....	53
10. Outlook	59
References	60

Executive summary

This document, titled Interim Impact Assessment Report, has been developed within the framework of the mAKE project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No. 101016858.

The evaluation and impact assessment of the mAKE project, which constitutes mAKE work package 7 (WP7), has two main objectives. First, we want to ensure that the project's network structures, capacity building support, created infrastructures, and materials are developed according to the project plan and are contributing to the project objectives. Second, we aim to provide evidence of the envisioned impact, and to identify facts and stories that demonstrate the project's influence beyond the borders of the consortium, particularly in terms of capacity building.

mAKE's evaluation and impact assessment approach is comprised of a summative evaluation of the benefits to participating individuals, organisations, and communities; and a formative evaluation of the implementation of support measures aimed at iteratively shaping activities, infrastructures, networks, and materials developed by the project.

In the mAKE project, evaluation has been integrated into project activities from its very beginning in early 2022. mAKE's approach to evaluation is understood as a form of participatory evaluation that initiates and supports, right from the start of the project, conversations on expectations, objectives, and impact. In the first project year (Y1), the mAKE consortium co-created the plan for evaluation and impact assessment, which contains the mAKE indicator framework, work package success criteria, and an introduction to potential data collection instruments (see deliverable D7.1: Impact Assessment Plan).

Based on this plan, the consortium continued its collaboration on evaluation and impact assessment in year two (Y2). WP7 organised regular online meetings with leaders of WPs 1 to 6 to discuss time points and instruments for collecting evaluation data from the different activities and facilitated sessions on evaluation and impact assessment during the hybrid (mix of in-person and online attendance) Berlin-based consortium meeting in June 2023 and the online consortium meeting of November 2023.

This Interim Impact Assessment Report provides an overview of the main project outputs, initial outcomes, and important lessons learnt across WPs 1 to 6 up to the end of Y2 (end-January 2024), and of the potential future sources of impact assessment data in in project year three (Y3) from February 2024 to January 2025.

It can be seen, across the core chapters of this Interim Impact Assessment Report, that the mAKE project has, through its first two years of work, successfully commenced delivery, in collaboration with its stakeholders, a broad portfolio of programmes. These programmes are grounded in the needs of

stakeholders, with those needs established collaboratively through numerous means, including in-depth stakeholder interviews, stakeholder focus group discussions (FGDs), online discussion channels, Community Call and Business Model webinars, and engagement with stakeholders at numerous events, in both Africa and Europe, devoted to fostering sustainable Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs)/makerspaces on both continents.

As seen in the initial outcomes presented in Chapters 3 to 8 of this interim report, there has been powerful networking, mutual-experience exchange, co-creation, awareness-raising, and learning amongst the diversified stakeholders, including the mAKE consortium members, operating in the African-European mAKErverse. These engagements, in addition to supporting the initial development and implementation of mAKE outputs, have resulted in very concrete and important learnings for the project, helping mAKE consortium members to adapt, where necessary, the created resources, infrastructures and materials to better suit the needs of the project's target individuals, organisations and communities. These important learnings can be found across all of WPs 1 to 6.

Two of the overarching learnings, which will need to continue to be addressed in Y3 if mAKE is to continue to successfully support the diverse and dynamic community of makers and DIHs/makerspaces in Africa and Europe—and to support inter-continental collaborations—are: the importance of building trust; and the need for flexibility. These two broad learnings, and more specific learnings as detailed in this interim report, will help ensure continued favourable outcomes in mAKE's Y3 work, and favourable impact in Y3 and beyond the life of the project. An example of one of the specific learnings, as mentioned in this report, was the realisation by WP3 (see Chapter 5) that its KPIs for the number of open educational resources (OERs) to be collected was too high and focusing too much on quantity rather than addressing the very specific needs of the target groups.

In the course of the remaining year of project activities, the WP7 evaluation team will continue supporting the consortium members, and in particular the WP leaders, in adapting suggested evaluation instruments to specific activities—so as to optimise collection of evidence on outputs and outcomes on a continuous basis, and to optimise learning from the formative aspects of mAKE's evaluation plan. The ultimate, long-term aim is for mAKE consortium members and stakeholders to provide increasingly mature and sustainable support to African and European DIHs/makerspaces, and to collaborations between DIHs/makerspaces on the two continents.

1. Introduction

This document presents the Interim Impact Assessment of the mAKE project at the end of the second project year (Y2). This document contains the following:

- **Chapter 1: Introduction**
- **Chapter 2: Vision**
Presents the main vision of the project consortium, as elaborated during the project's Kickoff Meeting at the beginning of the project.
- **Chapters 3–8: WP1–WP6**
Each of these six chapters presents the current status (as at the end of Y2) of activities, outputs and initial outcomes for a WP (WPs 1 through 6), provides insights into first lessons learnt in the WP, and introduces the evaluation plans for the WP during final project year (Y3).
- **Chapter 9: mAKE indicator framework at the end of Y2 and summary of lessons learnt**
Provides a summary of main outputs and initial outcomes across the WPs and the lessons learnt from formative evaluation.
- **Chapter 10: Outlook**
Looks ahead to Y3 activities of the evaluation and impact assessment work package (WP7).
- **References**

2. Vision

The mAKE consortium members, at the project's Kickoff Meeting in early 2022, defined a clear vision of what we want to achieve by the end of the three project years. This vision, and the objectives of the work programme, provide the bases for evaluating project success.

Figure 1: Collected expectations and brainstorming of project legacy during the Kickoff Meeting

The consortium’s definition of a project vision and legacy was followed by more detailed discussion, between WP7 and leaders of WPs 1–6, of success criteria for each work package. In Y1, following the logic model (Kurz & Kubek, 2016) approach and based on the mAKE workplan and Description of the Action (DoA), the WP7 team initiated the process of defining the main activities, outputs and outcomes for each WP and then collaborated with WP leaders in refining the expression of outcomes in the context of the expected, overall project vision. Also, for optimal planning of evaluation activities, potential means of data gathering were brainstormed with WP leaders in Y1. The details of this planning process can be found in deliverable D7.1: Impact Assessment Plan. In Y2, WP7 continued to have regular engagement with the WPs, via reflection meetings on their logic models and their means of generating impact assessment data. These meetings also served as a way for WP7 to advise regarding our data collection needs for this Interim Impact Assessment Report and the eventual Impact Assessment Package due at the end of Y3.

In the following chapters (3 to 8), we elaborate simplified logic models for each WP, featuring key outputs and initial outcomes from the WPs as of the end of Y2, and each WP’s Y3 evaluation data collection plans. Chapter 9 presents a summary of the mAKE indicator framework as at the end of Y2, including key outputs and initial outcomes set out in the WP chapters (3–8). Chapter 10 concludes with a brief outlook towards WP7’s work in Y3.

3. Venture building and business models (WP1)

This work package (WP1) aims to collect, analyse, and provide information on the objectives and operating models of successful organisations in the startup, SME, Digital Innovation Hub (DIH), and makerspace arena in order to generate a rich resource to support early-stage startups (and related entities) towards establishment of their businesses. WP1 provides targeted matchmaking opportunities between digital innovators, SMEs, businesses, investors, public bodies, academic institutions and NGOs in Europe and Africa, and aims to identify investors and potential investors to catalyse more private capital for investment in digital social innovation (DSI).

3.1 Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM)

One key activity of WP1 in the second project year was the development of the Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM). During the conceptualisation and creation of this catalogue, WP1 established close contact with relevant stakeholder groups, including all members of the MAKE consortium, and members of the communities represented in the consortium, including GIG, AfricaOSH, AMN, and the Fab City network. Six in-person co-creation workshops were held (in Germany, Indonesia, Cameroon, and South Africa—in each case taking advantage of other events where the target audience for the catalogue was gathered). WP1 also organised regular online community discussions (“business models webinars”) where input was collected on specific business models or business model elements, such as consultancy, manufacturing networks, and working with artisans. In addition, 50 individual interviews were conducted with representatives of makerspaces and other organisations in the distributed manufacturing ecosystem. These interviews were the main sources of content and framing for the catalogue, supplemented by the co-creation workshops and online community discussions.

After the first version of the OCBM was published, WP1 commenced a mentoring programme, with three makerspaces, for trialling use of the catalogue. As part of this mentoring programme, the participating makerspaces are expected to provide inputs on their expectations for use of the catalogue and, eventually, on their experiences of using it—thus generating valuable assessment data.

A mAKE consortium member, the Internet of Production Alliance (IOP), received funding, under the UK International Development-funded [Research and Innovation Systems for Africa \(RISA\) Fund](#), for a programme including creating a website version of the OCBM. This website was launched in December 2023, and can be seen at <https://localeconomies.org>. This website is the “living document” version of the OCBM, and additional information and functionality can be added as needed.

3.1.1 OCBM mentoring programme

The mentoring programme is generating case studies of implementation of the business model catalogue in three different local contexts. The programme, which started in November 2023, is running for six months and has three makerspaces as mentees (Habitat Augsburg in Germany, Garoua in Cameroon, and iZone Hub in Zimbabwe). There were sessions with each of the mentee makerspace representatives at the end of 2023, introducing them to tools for environmental business analysis (analysing the structure around the organisation (community, customers etc.) via, e.g., SWOT analysis). Each makerspace has been paired with an individual mentor from the mAKE consortium, and the mentee-mentor pairings have begun to meet regularly (fortnightly is suggested as a guideline).

The next stage in the programme is to support the makerspaces with elements from the catalogue, to adapt these elements according to the local context and needs of the makerspaces, and to implement them. A report on the three implementation case studies will then be delivered in April 2024, providing insights into the main lessons learnt from the mentoring programme. This report will include the mentee makerspaces' perceptions of impact, i.e., perceptions of the extent to which the mentoring programme, together with the business model catalogue, enabled makerspaces to run their businesses more sustainably. When asked to provide their initial expectations for their participation in the OCBM mentoring programme, representatives of the three mentee makerspaces wrote the following:

- **Habitat Augsburg:** "Until now, our goal has always been for the Habitat not to depend on grants and to sustain itself. I hope that the mentoring program can provide the final necessary refinement to our business model so that the Habitat can finally achieve sustainable financial independence. Additionally, I am more than excited that we can expand our African-European connections and look forward to what the Habitat can learn from the other participants."
- **Garoua:** "We expect that at the end of this program, we will be well organized, and we will be able to stand on our own and be autonomous".
- **iZone Hub:** "Through our participation in the mentoring program, we aspire to expand our horizons. We aim to learn from the experiences and insights of others, allowing us to refine and enhance our makerspace. Our goal is to build a more inclusive and thriving community where individuals of all backgrounds and skill levels can come to explore, create, and innovate. We hope to gain new perspectives and strategies that will further enrich the iZone Hub makerspace experience, making it a go-to destination for all aspiring makers and innovators."

The OCBM activities, outputs and initial outcomes at the end of Y2 are summarised in the matrix below.

WP1 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Future means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
<p>Document and disseminate an Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM)</p> <p>Documentation of how existing successful businesses and makerspaces are operating as examples to other early-stage startups, as well as documentation of profitable makerspaces</p> <p>State-of-the art analysis of already existing documentation</p> <p>Recording of webinars to disseminate the OCBM and tell people how to use it</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <p>D1.1: Open Catalogue of Business Models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 workshops held with over 100 participants in total, gathering information on how the OCBM could be most useful • 50 individual interviews with successful DIHs/makerspaces representing a cross-section of sectors, geographic foci, and scales • 17 published example business models for hardware DIHs/makerspaces and for ventures interaction with DIHs/makerspaces • 8 webinars organised, with more than 200 participants in the webinars • 3 makerspaces selected for pre-testing (implementation-testing) in the mentoring programme; 3 calls conducted with the full cohort, plus additional one-on-one calls between each makerspace and its mentor <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on makerspace requirements discovered during the OCBM pre-testing mentorship programme, “tags” were added to the online OCBM to allow for filtering by the context for which the model will be used • Positive initial feedback from users of the catalogue: Makerspaces and those supporting makerspaces confirming that they are using the information and that it will be helpful to them. • The Ukrainian Maker Association has translated the OCBM into Ukrainian, https://makerua.org/business-models-for-makerspaces, to share with its members; and mAkE is now in discussions with organisations who would like to translate the catalogue into French, Spanish and Portuguese, so as to share it with communities where English is not widely understood 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access and social media statistics • Continuation of implementation-testing of OCBM with mentee makerspaces • Individual impact pathway interviews with users of the catalogue • FGD with several catalogue users to discuss lessons learnt

3.1.2 First lessons learnt

We have learnt that the leaders of makerspaces are more accustomed to teaching and mentoring others than to being in the “learner” position themselves. This shift in role (from being the person with all the answers to one with lots of questions) can be uncomfortable, and there is a need for the mentors to support their mentees in taking on that new role.

The three mentee makerspaces are starting from different places, working on implementation of different business models, and working at different paces. The structure originally planned for the all-mentee progress review sessions has needed to be relaxed to allow for these differences. Nonetheless, both mentors and mentees have stated that they see a lot of benefit from creating opportunities for meaningful exchange among and between the mentees. Thus, we are experimenting with different formats to allow for

those exchanges to happen, with enough structure to make the exchanges useful but also enough flexibility to allow for differences in where the mentees are at.

We realised it would be helpful to create a new “pathway” into the catalogue of business models. One of the mentee makerspaces in particular has approached the catalogue not from the perspective of “We want to implement this business model” but rather from the perspective of “We want to undertake this activity, and what are the business models we could use to support it?” The information in the OCBM is just as valid for answering this question, but we realised we could make it easier to approach this kind of question by enabling a filtering of the business models by context. Accordingly, the LocalEconomies.org web site referenced above now has a system of “tags” being applied to different models in the catalogue, so as to allow for filtering in terms of the contexts in which each model can be used.

3.1.3 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3

As mentioned above, the mentoring programme will run until April 2024, and will be completed through writing up of three case studies that will include, among other things, the three mentee makerspaces’ perceptions of outcomes and impact. This mentoring programme will, thus, provide valuable information on the usefulness of the business model catalogue and its application in three different local contexts. The lessons learnt for making the catalogue more useful, or user-friendly, will then be incorporated into the website. When asked in January 2024 about the potential impact of the OCBM, Ronald Tsatsi, Makerspace Lead at iZone Hub Zimbabwe (one of the three mentee sites) wrote as follows: “I have found the Open Catalogue of Business Models to be a valuable resource, especially in understanding different models and how they can be combined. This tool has the potential to greatly benefit iZone Hub and similar initiatives, providing insights that can drive innovation and strategic planning.”

In addition, three to six months after the end of the mentoring programme, follow-up impact-pathway interviews will be conducted with the three makerspaces, so as to capture the potential longer-term benefits of the programme. For quantitative data, WP7 will track the online access numbers for the catalogue.

3.2 Venture Building and Business Development programme

The Venture Building and Business Development programme aims to:

- Engage with 20 companies (startups and SMEs) in Europe and Africa, providing personalised one-on-one support tailored to each company's specific needs. This programme includes not only advisory services but also aims to connect companies with investors and/or potential partners.
- Collaborate with 10 trainers from DIHs/makerspaces, offering practical advisory sessions to enhance their expertise in supporting startups and SMEs.

In November 2023, 25 out of 53 applying companies were shortlisted based on the GreenTec Success Matrix and afterwards ranked by the mAKE high-level Stakeholder Jury. Based on the Jury's judgements, as well as taking into account factors such as the ratio of female-led companies, 20 companies were selected for the Venture Building programme. A general kickoff session, to which all 20 companies were invited, as well as individual calls with the companies, took place in December 2023 and January 2024. The individual calls aimed to assess the needs of the ventures, create rough roadmaps for the specific support needed, and understand which kinds of experts should be allocated to support the companies.

An impact-tracking tool was conceptualised, and implementation of the tool commenced at the beginning of the programme through a baseline survey collecting additional details on the selected companies, including a specific section on the expectations of each venture. These expectations will constitute the baseline for the evaluation at the end of the Venture Building programme. Both the individual calls and the baseline component of the impact-tracking tool were used to get first data for evaluation and impact assessment (see 3.2.1 below).

Additionally, WP1 will organise train-the-trainer events for business development with 10 makerspaces, to build their capacity to support startups and SMEs. These trainings will start in March 2024 and will be evaluated via a training survey. As of the end of January 2024, the training content and setup had been elaborated, and potential train-the-trainer collaborations developed.

WP1 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Future means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
<p>Set up and offer a company builder programme for ventures</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 53 companies (startups and SMEs) applied for the Venture Building and Business Development programme ● 3 GreenTec experts involved in shortlisting of 25 companies ● 1 kickoff call with Stakeholder Jury ● 4 out of 5 Jury members filled out the ranking template for the 25 shortlisted companies (1 jury member was unable to rank due to illness) based on GreenTec Success Matrix, which includes impact, product market fit, scalability, and financial maturity ● 20 companies selected for the programme ● 20 confirmation emails sent, with acceptance into the programme conditional on, among other things, the company's commitment to post-programme impact reporting ● 1 general onboarding session convened, with 11 companies and 4 experts joining ● 1 onboarding presentation shared with companies ● 19 individual need assessment sessions conducted ● D 1.2: Venture Building Handbook, for use in training of makerspace-based trainers, elaborated and designed (M24) <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● all 20 selected companies have made a commitment to participation in post-programme impact reporting ● the companies' responses to the baseline survey component of the impact-tracking tool (17 of 20 have responded at the time of writing this report) have demonstrated to us that networking opportunities and business growth are strong programme expectations among participating companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Internal reports and documentation by consortium members involved in the task ● Exit survey and interviews with the 20 involved companies ● Follow-up impact-pathway interviews with up to 10 of the involved companies 3-5 months after the end of the Venture Building programme ● Formative evaluation of the train-the-trainer workshops at makerspaces ● FGDs with personnel at makerspaces who participated in the train-the-trainer workshops

3.2.1 First lessons learnt

The following elaboration is based on the evaluation of 17 companies' responses to the baseline survey in the impact-tracking tool. We are awaiting answers from three more companies.

What are your expectations for the programme?		
Area	% of responses	No. of responses
Operational efficiency	70.59	12
Business growth	88.24	15
Investor-readiness	76.47	13
Pitch perfection	52.94	9
Networking opportunities	94.12	16

In which areas do you believe you could benefit from additional support? (our experts will also assess potential intervention points)		
Area	% of responses	No. of responses
Strategic	64.71	11
Operational	52.94	9
Financial	82.35	14
Digital marketing	52.94	9
Pitch training	47.06	8
Investment	94.12	16

In essence, the baseline survey found that the companies are eagerly anticipating valuable networking prospects and business growth. The expectations align well with the other features of the mAKE Venture Building and Business Development programme, which includes pitch events and, for ventures that are interested, founder-to-founder (F2F) matchmaking and business-to-business (B2B) networking. In terms of support, it is evident that many startups encounter challenges in financial and fundraising domains, both of which are areas our experienced experts are well-equipped to address.

3.2.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3

As mentioned above, participants of the Venture Building programme shared their expectations in the baseline component of the impact-tracking tool, as distributed at the beginning of the programme. A final survey, and discussions of perceived benefits, will be implemented with all 20 companies during the final mentoring call of the Venture Building programme, and thus will be an important source of information on the perceived usefulness of the programme and companies' perceptions of the outcomes and potential impacts generated by participation.

Follow-up impact-pathway interviews with selected participants will be organised three months after the end of the Venture Building programme, in order to capture participants' perceptions of the long-term benefits of involvement. Evaluation of the train-the-trainer events and the material of the Venture Building programme shared online will be conducted via a survey and additional short interviews with selected makerspaces.

3.3 Makers-in-Residency (MiR) programme

The Makers-in-Residency (MiR) programme endeavours to both foster connections between African and European makers through mutual learning and provide valuable opportunities for enhanced input, expertise, and potential access to essential machinery. This collective effort aims to propel makers' impactful prototypes forward into the next stages of development. The MiR programme has, to date, been implemented in two waves. In MiR 1.0, four makers and one makerspace were selected out of the 66 makers and 31 makerspaces who applied for the programme. MiR 2.0 started at the end of 2023, and at the time of writing this report, 16 makers have been shortlisted out of 45 makers who applied.

WP1 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Future means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
<p>Offer targeted marketing and matchmaking services</p> <p>Mapping of African and European makerspaces, developing a strategy on how to approach them</p> <p>Definition of the selection process, and selection of participants in the Makers-in-Residency (MiR) programme</p> <p>Organisation of: Founder-to-founder (F2F) matchmaking opportunities Business-to-business (B2B) networking opportunities</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <p>Makers-in-Residency (MiR) 1.0</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 66 makers and 31 makerspaces applied for the MiR 1.0 programme • 4 makers and 1 makerspace selected to participate • 5 Stakeholder Jury members involved <p>MiR 2.0</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 45 makers and 4 makerspaces have to date applied for the MiR 2.0 programme (only 4 European makerspaces have applied but due to Vulca's contacts, we will be able to find more that are interested—see explanation below) • 16 makers have been shortlisted for MiR 2.0 • 0 Stakeholder Jury members involved to date (will be involved once potential matches for shortlisted makers have been identified) <p>F2F matchmaking</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 events <p>B2B networking</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 event <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges encountered in delivery of MiR 1.0 led to recognition of need to reach out to a makerspace network (i.e., Vulca) with a strong European presence • Collaboration with Vulca has greatly improved engagement with European makers and makerspaces (for MiR 2.0) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal reports and documentation by consortium members involved in the task • Individual impact-pathway interviews with participants of the MiR programme • Questionnaires for evaluation of outcomes from participation in F2F matchmaking and B2B networking

3.3.1 First lessons learnt

A key learning from MiR 1.0 was the difficulty of aligning makers with suitable makerspaces, considering factors such as machinery, expertise, community dynamics, and language. To ensure a productive residency for the makers, mAKE consortium members GreenTec and GIG have formed a partnership with the Vulca network, <https://vulca.eu>, a key facilitator of European makerspaces. GreenTec and GIG participated in the annual Vulca Seminar to promote the mAKE MiR programme and engage with makerspaces from the Vulca network, fostering crucial in-person connections. Recognising the significance of personal relationships in achieving successful matches, we are currently working collaboratively with Vulca in the matching process for MiR 2.0.

We also learnt that, in terms of programme design, flexibility in duration is necessary. Different projects demand varying intensities and durations, and makers have diverse requirements based on individual life situations, such as family commitments, student responsibilities, or employment obligations. Allowing for flexibility in duration is making the programme more accommodating of, and responsive to, the needs of participants.

Another learning, gained through receiving feedback from makerspaces during the Vulca Seminar, is that makerspaces prefer, before submitting applications, to be briefed by a known and trusted entity (in this instance, Vulca) about projects and application procedures. Collaborating with Vulca, which possesses in-depth knowledge of its community members, has also diminished the level of detail necessary in the MiR application form, thus making the application process less cumbersome and daunting for makerspaces.

We have also learnt that due to the difficulties that African passport-holders currently face in receiving visas from European countries, significant time and effort need to be expended by any project that seeks to facilitate in-person interaction by African makers with European makerspace contexts. Despite the mAKE project's intensive collaborative efforts since August 2023, only one of the three makers due to take up a residency in MiR 1.0 at a makerspace in Athens has, at the time of writing, received a visa for entry into Europe.

A final valuable learning is that makers, who tend to be extremely dynamic individuals involved in numerous activities, often experience rapid changes in their employment situations, which can affect their ability to participate in a project. As an example of this, one of the four makers originally chosen for MiR 1.0 had to withdraw because, during the course of the delayed visa process, the maker's employment situation changed, making it no longer possible for this maker to take up the planned MiR residency in Athens.

3.3.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3

To evaluate the MiR programme, two focus group discussions (FGDs) will be organised in July–August 2024: one with the makers in the programme, and one with the host makerspaces. The aim of these FGDs will be to discuss the benefits and challenges encountered during participation in the MiR programme. In addition, impact–pathway interviews with selected makers will be organised three months after they complete their residencies, in order to capture the makers' views on the potential long-term benefits of MiR participation.

4. Hub ecosystem and policy frameworks (WP2)

Across the African and European continents, makerspaces have emerged as vital hubs of innovation, fostering local creativity, technological advancements, and economic growth. However, amidst this dynamic landscape, one challenge persists: the absence of common policies that can effectively support and nurture the thriving maker innovation ecosystem. Currently, makerspaces in Africa and Europe often

operate within distinct policy frameworks, resulting in a lack of common direction and collaboration. As the mAKE project, we recognise the significance of policy advocacy in empowering makerspaces to reach their full potential and drive positive societal impact.

As such, this work package (WP2) aims to improve connections between DIHs/makerspaces and public sector actors and local political decision-makers, so as to build recognition and favourable policies in support of national and regional startup ecosystems. WP2 is working to facilitate an informed dialogue on DIH/makerspace policy needs and demands, as well as the role of DIHs/makerspaces in fulfilling policy agendas such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In Y1, WP conducted case studies of seven DIH/makerspace associations, how these associations organise themselves, and how they engage policymaking processes. These studies were documented in deliverable D2.1: Report on National and Regional Hub Associations including 7 Documented Case Studies and Comparative Analyses, completed at the end of Y1 (M12, January 2023).

In Y2, existing policy frameworks were mapped to ascertain key policy areas where interventions could potentially improve the work of DIHs/makerspaces as local innovators. WP2 organised a series of workshops and FGDs that collected the requirements and needs of DIHs/makerspaces, in terms of barriers and enablers faced, in both Africa and Europe. The aim was to gather insight from DIH/makerspace stakeholders for the identification, through a bottom-up approach, of practice-based policy needs and a common policy agenda. A total of 18 sessions (interviews and FGDs) were conducted, engaging a diverse group of 69 participants, with 26 of the participants representing African DIHs/makerspaces and 43 representing European DIH/makerspaces.

Based on these interviews and FGDs, a first draft of deliverable D2.2, Common Policy Agenda and Recommendations for Policy Makers, was formulated. The main features of this draft document were put to discussion by stakeholders in a mAKE webinar in mid-December 2023 that brought together 26 participants from across Africa and Europe. The participants comprised makers, DIH/makerspace leaders (managers, CEOs), a local government representative, and three experts (one from Europe and two from Africa) who made presentations.

WP2 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Future means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
<p>Collection, mapping and comparative analysis of case studies focused on how DIHs/makerspaces organise themselves in supportive structures for policy advocacy on national and regional levels</p>	<p>Outputs: D2.1: Report on National and Regional Hub Associations including 7 Documented Case Studies and Comparative Analyses (M12)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 case studies from Africa; 2 from Europe • Recommendations for bottom-up approaches to multi-actor policy advocacy for DIHs/makerspaces <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings from Y1 case studies helped shape the themes and questions pursued in the Y2 FGDs and interviews (see below) • Y1 case studies generated valuable contacts for setting up the Y2 FGDs and interviews 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal reports and documentation of DIHs/makerspaces and collective associations involved on the case studies • Access and social media statistics to the report
<p>Creation of a common policy agenda for makerspaces in Africa and Europe and recommendations for policy makers</p>	<p>Outputs: D2.2: Common Policy Agenda and Recommendations for Policy Makers (M24)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 11 FGDs (10 virtual and one in-person at an event) • 7 interviews (virtual) • A total of 69 participants in the FGDs/interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 26 participants from Africa • 43 participants from Europe • 26 participants (makers, DIH/makerspace leaders, local government representative, experts) in 13-Dec-2023 mAKE webinar focused on development of common policy agenda • involving a local government representative, makers, educators, managers and CEOs of makerspaces • Engagement with makerspaces on mAKE project at AfriLabs Annual Gathering, Kigali, Oct. 2023 • Presentation of mAKE project at Ghana Digital Innovation Week (GDIW), Accra, Nov. 2023, with attendance by 35 GDIW delegates • Awareness-raising on mAKE project during Africa Makerspace Network (AMN) Study Programme, May 2023, with mAKE session attended by 16 participants • Deliverable D2.2 completed <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder inputs during December 2023 mAKE webinar ensured that the WP remains cognizant of the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access and social media statistics for the policy recommendations • “Minister Meet Makers” dialogue events to discuss the recommendations • Interviews with selected policy makers to discuss the recommendations • Formative evaluation of the “Minister Meets Makers” events via short interviews • Impact-pathway interviews with selected policy makers who participated in the “Minister Meet Makers” events

WP2 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Future means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
	<p>need to collaborate with local decision-makers and local institutions in policy formulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder inputs during December 2023 webinar prompted the WP to work towards development of a policy brief 	

4.1 First lessons learnt

The inputs to the 13-Dec-2023 mAKE webinar included mention of the importance of engaging local leaders during public events in order to foster collaboration. Such engagement can serve as a catalyst for initiating meaningful discussions with opinion leaders focused on policy formulation. This kind of engagement can also ensure local support and buy-in, which are crucial for successful policy implementation.

A key learning from our FGDs, interviews, and other engagements with makers is the need to categorise policies based on which stakeholders should take the lead in their implementation. The three primary areas identified are: (1) the local/national government level; (2) the European/African Union continental level; and the (3) makerspace level. This strategic categorisation can streamline efforts and enhance accountability in policy execution. Such a categorisation will allow for tailored implementation strategies, acknowledging the contextual nuances and maximising the impact of the proposed policies.

Webinar participants also highlighted the need to align new policies with already-existing frameworks. By integrating with established policies, DIHs/makerspaces can navigate regulatory landscapes more seamlessly, fostering a conducive environment for their initiatives.

Another finding from the aforementioned December 2023 webinar was the need to develop a policy brief, so as to build broader understanding and support for the proposed policy positions. A compelling policy brief is viewed as a key tool for engaging a diverse audience.

Building on these lessons, the Report on Common Policy Agenda and Recommendations for Policy Makers—completed and published in January 2024 (M24)—includes elements responding to the key insights and strategies discussed during the webinar. In addition, a draft of the recommended policy brief was provided to mAKE internal reviewers in late January 2024.

4.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3

In Y3, it is anticipated that there will be four “Minister meet Makers” dialogue events for presentation and discussion of the mAKE policy agenda recommendations, and these events will also be used as occasions to have interviews with political decision-makers. In these interviews, the decision-makers will be presented with the mAKE policy recommendations and will be asked to what extent they feel the recommendations can be acted upon in the decision-makers’ local/national/regional/continental context(s).

In addition, certain of the Y2 FGD participants and interviewees will be approached in Y3 for interviews to explore the extent to which the mAKE policy recommendations have affected their understanding of relations between DIHs/makerspaces and policy/policymakers.

5. Open education, skill development and capacity building (WP3)

This work package (WP3) is dedicated to the training and up-skilling of DIHs/makerspaces and the makers, innovators, entrepreneurs, SMEs and startups they interact with. It aims at developing a joint learning space for African and European DIH/makerspace networks—a space that supports the development of the technical, ethical, and entrepreneurial skills necessary for advanced digital fabrication and sustainable digital innovation.

5.1 Open Makerspace Toolkit and training of trainers

The three main tasks of WP3 are: develop the Open Makerspace Toolkit composed of open educational resources (OERs); train makerspace-based trainers in use of the Toolkit and how to train others to use it; and build a massive open online course (MOOC) platform that aggregates OERs, including Toolkit resources, generated during the project.

The Open Makerspace Toolkit, now available online, contains elements of existing OERs, and OERs created by the mAKE project, on how to set up, manage, equip and sustain different types of open, collaborative and innovative makerspaces. During the development of the Toolkit, we:

- Connected with external stakeholders via a survey to collect OERs. This survey is still open and has to date received 15 high-quality responses from external stakeholders.
- Collected and reviewed existing OERs that were potentially relevant to the Toolkit.
- Selected, for inclusion in the Toolkit, elements of existing OERs with strong relevance to the maker movement and/or social innovation.
- Selected, for inclusion in the Toolkit, elements of existing OERs created by the mAKE project.

The Open Makerspace Toolkit has been published, as an open access resource, on the Pressbooks platform, <https://pressbooks.pub>, which is an OER-focused platform that allows for easy updating of content. Using the Pressbooks platform makes the Toolkit a non-static, living resource that can grow and improve as more elements become available from external sources and from the work of mAKE consortium members. The Toolkit is available at <https://pressbooks.pub/omt4make>.

Upon publication of the Toolkit, focus shifted towards organisation of the training-of-trainers activities that will, in Y3, train initial cohorts of DIH/makerspace-linked trainers in how to train others to use the Toolkit. The participants in these first cohorts of trainers will then organise in-country trainings with selected representatives of makerspaces at national level in their home countries (5–10 trainees per country). The first training-of-trainers event will take place in March 2024 at the premises of mAKE consortium member the Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC) in Barcelona, in conjunction with a mAKE consortium meeting. A second training-of-trainers event is planned for May 2024 at MboaLab in Yaoundé, where consortium member (and WP3 leader) the Association pour la Promotion de la Science Ouverte en Haïti et en Afrique (APSOHA) is headquartered.

In addition to training Toolkit users in their home countries, these initial cohorts of trained trainers will be expected to conduct their own online and in-Person train-the-trainers events, in order to extend the reach of training capacity for the Toolkit. The outreach by trained trainers will be supported by the consortium members, who will reach out to additional makerspaces in Africa and Europe.

The participants in the March 2024 training-of-trainers will provide feedback on the Toolkit directly after the training event and, later in Y3, an FGD or individual impact-pathway interviews will be conducted with these trainers—as an important source of information on outcomes and impact of Toolkit usage in various local contexts.

WP3 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Potential means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
<p>Develop an Open Makerspace Toolkit, comprising OERs on how to set up, manage, equip, and sustain different types of digital innovation makerspaces</p>	<p>Outputs: D3.1: Open Makerspace Toolkit</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Online survey to collect OERs: 15 high-quality responses received from external stakeholders ● Collection and review of approximately 400 existing OERs with potential relevance to the Toolkit ● Selection of elements of approximately 80 existing OERs for inclusion in the Toolkit, with emphasis on elements with strong relevance to the maker movement and/or social innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Internal reports and documentation by consortium members involved in the task ● Access statistics for the online Toolkit, and statistics for social media linked to the Toolkit ● Survey questionnaire completed by people who are trained in use of the Toolkit, for formative evaluation of usefulness of Toolkit (questionnaire to be administered by trainers who

WP3 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Potential means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusion, in the Toolkit, of elements of 3 OERs created by the mAKE project • Online publication of Open Makerspace Toolkit (M24), comprising OERs on how to set up, manage, equip, and sustain different types of digital innovation makerspaces: https://pressbooks.pub/omt4make <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The discovery of the rapid pace of development of new OERs relevant to DIHs/makerspaces made it necessary to host the Toolkit on a platform that allows for easy updating. Accordingly, the Pressbooks platform, https://pressbooks.com, was chosen • It was determined that the target number of OERs included in the Toolkit needed to be revised downwards from the originally projected target, so as to be able to focus more on quality than quantity 	<p>participate in training-of-trainers events (see below))</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An FGD, or individual impact-pathway interviews, with users of the Toolkit, to learn about applicability and usage in different contexts
<p>Plan and organise training-of-trainers events</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning and organising of first training-of-trainers event, March 2024, in Barcelona (with 10-15 participants) • Planning and organising of second training-of-trainers event, May 2024, in Yaoundé (with 20-25 participants) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal reports and documentation by consortium members involved in the task • Survey questionnaire completed by training-of-trainer workshop participants for formative evaluation of workshops and of usefulness of Toolkit • An FGD, or individual impact-pathway interviews, with trainers as users of the Toolkit, to learn about applicability and usage in different contexts

5.1.1 First lessons learnt

It was found during the first two years of the project that we were overly ambitious in our initial projected numbers with respect to the number of existing OERs, and OERs created by the mAKE project, that should be selected for inclusion in the Toolkit. It was determined that the emphasis needed to be on quality rather than quantity. Accordingly, we revised the OER targets downwards. The table below shows the initial targets, the revised targets, and the totals reached by the end of Y2.

Resources	Initial target	Revised target	Resources identified by end of Y2
Existing OERs with potential relevance to the Toolkit	800	400	approximately 400
Existing OERs with elements selected for inclusion in the Toolkit, with emphasis on elements with strong relevance to the maker movement and/or social innovation	200	100	approximately 80
OERs created by the mAKE consortium that contain element selected for inclusion in the Toolkit	100	10	3

Another key lesson learnt was the need to have an easily edited online version of the Toolkit. Initially, we planned to develop a largely static version of the Toolkit for publication online. However, there will likely be new online resources emerging during Y3 that have elements with direct relevance for the Toolkit, and thus the Toolkit would become obsolete if we did not update it regularly. Accordingly, we opted for hosting the online version of the Toolkit on the OER-focused Pressbooks platform, <https://pressbooks.com>, whose content management system allows for rapid content additions and updates.

5.1.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3

A survey will be completed by training-of-trainers participants, so as to generate formative feedback on the training directly after its completion—thus providing insights on the usefulness of the training and the perceived interest to follow up on work with the Toolkit. Also, where applicable, surveys will be administered to participants in the training events conducted locally by trainers who have participated in the training-of-trainers activities. In addition, so as to get in-depth insights into the usage of the Toolkit and its impact, a follow-up FGD, or individual impact-pathway interviews, will be conducted with trainers three to six months after their participation in training-of-trainers activities. An FGD, or individual impact-pathway interviews, will also be conducted with Toolkit users.

6. Distributed manufacturing network (WP4)

This work package (WP4) aims to foster distributed manufacturing among DIHs/makerspaces by prototyping and supporting adoption of digital infrastructures that enable sharing of skills, machinery, and contracts within DIH/makerspace networks.

6.1 People and Skills Specification (PSS) and Maker Passport prototype

6.1.1 People and Skills Specification (PSS): Overview

The aim of the People and Skills Specification (PSS) is to create an open data specification for the mutual recognition of skills and experiences held by makers, by establishing an understanding of vocabulary and a shared taxonomy of skills and experiences, as well as a framework for the verification of this knowledge. This specification¹ is intentionally designed to provide the groundwork for sharing those skills and experiences with potential employers or customers, fellow makers, and educational institutions via the Open Badge System Framework.² The PSS can also be used as a stand-alone, should an open-badging system not be an option. By design, the PSS could be adopted and adapted by anyone who wishes to have a credentialing system that enables nomadic makers to travel between makerspaces. This navigation will be enabled by using a digital “Maker Passport”, the preliminary criteria for which were defined by maker community members during the research process preceding the PSS beta release.

6.1.2 Maker Passport for mutual skills recognition: Overview

The Maker Passport aims to put the PSS into practice as a mechanism for enabling recognition of skills and experiences held by makers. A method for information exchange, which serves as a prototype for creating a Maker Passport, was released in June 2023 and is described in deliverable D4.1: Skills – Mutual Recognition Standard.³

Essentially, using the PSS as a data schema, a simple web form can be established to create a user record, and the recommended output for this record is JSON. The `pss-user-schema.json`⁴ is openly available in the Internet of Production (IOP) GitHub⁵, with licensing and README information regarding the Maker Passport `.json` available in the `maker-passport` repository.⁶

¹ PSS Data Specification v4, released June 2023: <https://standards.internetofproduction.org/pub/r7gOn9fo/release/4>

² See Peer 2 Peer University & The Mozilla Foundation (n.d.). An open badge system framework. Paper drafted in collaboration with The MacArthur Foundation, <http://bit.ly/badgepaper4>

³ Deliverable D4.1: Skills – Mutual Recognition Standard: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Ag7WbbCefkjtmIp3G6RvPPSpjW60IfHs/view?usp=drive_link

⁴ `pss-user-schema.json`: <https://github.com/iop-alliance/maker-passport/blob/main/pss-user-schema.json>

⁵ Internet of Production Alliance repositories on GitHub: <https://github.com/iop-alliance>

⁶ `maker-passport` repository: <https://github.com/iop-alliance/maker-passport/tree/main>

The PSS User Record accompanies the officially and unofficially credentialed skills and experiences that are documented in structured or unstructured formats.

The purpose is to allow automated indexing of key properties about the user and to identify and link to the associated issuing clients.

The user record shall be used to define user record changes over time.

The user record should be updated when any credential status or user descriptor data changes.

Figure 2: Maker Passport – record form for users

While the PSS is designed to integrate easily for use with open-badging platforms, it could also be used as a stand-alone, with either an online form that is stored locally (as opposed to the cloud), or even on paper. If the information were to be digitised later on, so long as the specification was used, all categories of information necessary for integration into an online system would be there. In technical terms, this means that the PSS is designed to be interoperable with common open-badging standard protocols but can also be used without internet connectivity to maintain paper records in-house, for makerspaces that either do not have the infrastructure to support an open-badging system or require manual record load for maintaining local records. This online vs. offline application of the Maker Passport was applied and tested in the Innovative Manufacturing in Africa (IMA) project⁷ in the fall of 2023, and the outcomes of this application are detailed below in section 6.1.3.

6.1.3 Evidence-informed development

For the development of the PSS and digital maker wallet/passport concept for prototype, experiences and feedback of makerspace leaders and stakeholders—on the skills needed for production and how they are

⁷ IMA project page: <https://www.internetofproduction.org/innovative-manufacturing-awards>

verified were captured via semi-structured interviews and FGDs. The aim was to identify emergent thematic categories for the development of a survey to gather larger datasets from the DIH/makerspace community. Document analysis⁸ was also conducted across open community platforms, unpublished/grey literature, white papers and open publications related to makerspace passport programmes, micro credentialing, and digital badging programmes.

Figure 3: Development steps of the Maker Passport

Semi-structured interviews

The experiences and feedback of makerspace leaders and stakeholders were captured via 25 semi-structured interviews to help in identifying emergent thematic categories for the development of a survey to gather larger datasets from the maker community.

Workshop and focus group facilitation

[Workshop materials](#) were developed to facilitate the discussion of the Maker Passport concept at stakeholder events. The workshop content, “Building a Makerspace Passport: What training and skills do people need?” includes multiple active-learning exercises, with the following goals:

- Communicating the work towards development of deliverable D4.1: Skills – Mutual Recognition Standard and making it personally relevant to attendees
- Gathering information relevant to deliverable D4.1

This workshop was offered during the Africa Makerspace Network’s (AMN’s) annual Africa Makerspace Gathering (AMG) in November 2022 in Cape Town. All [workshop materials](#) are openly licensed for re-use by any facilitator.

⁸ Reference list for document analysis: <https://standards.internetofproduction.org/pub/fyqzwcyd/release/1>

Surveys

Drawing from preliminary findings generated by the desktop research, interviews and workshop, a survey was distributed to makers and makerspaces in early February 2023 with the aim of gathering a larger quantitative dataset that would be complementary to the qualitative data that had been gathered thus far. The survey was framed using the emergent categories of Who, What, Why, and How that had been identified by exploratory research. We received 66 responses from individual makers and 31 responses from makerspace leaders (97 responses in total).

In parallel, a PSS Working Group was initiated by the IOP Alliance with a call for participation sent out in February 2023 to the IOP community and the mAKE consortium partners. In addition to the IOP mAKE project team, this PSS Working Group comprises researchers affiliated with university makerspaces and members of civil society organisations (including Grassroots Economics, <https://www.grassrootseconomics.org>, and Open Source Ecology, <https://www.opensourceecology.org>) focussing on technological solutions. In the first half of 2023, the PSS Working Group met twice to review and discuss the PSS. Following these meetings, the work was conducted asynchronously to finalise the standard and support its testing within the IMA project (see below). Starting in November 2023, the PSS Working Group has been meeting monthly, with a focus on preparing the roadmap for the next prototype.

Testing the PSS and Maker Passport via the IMA project

As part of the mAKE-affiliated Innovative Manufacturing in Africa (IMA) project, which is run by the IOP Alliance and funded by RISA, nine makerspaces in Ghana, Kenya and South Africa (three in each country) used a prototype of a Maker Passport based on the released PSS standard and conducted a first functional test of the Passport sign-up interface. In these first tests by the nine IMA makerspaces, we counted 45 sign-ups for the PSS/Maker Passport via the [sign-up form](#).

Feedback from the cohort (the nine IMA makerspaces, and members of these makerspaces who signed onto the Maker Passport), as well as actions taken to apply suggested changes to the Maker Passport prototype, are detailed below in section 6.1.4 of this report. During interviews in late 2023, the nine participating makerspaces provided detailed feedback on their experiences. Feedback from the tests will continue to be integrated into the prototype, before it is eventually rolled out to a larger audience via the networks of the mAKE consortium members. In preparation for a second wave of dissemination of the Maker Passport sign-up interface in mid-2024, conversations will be fostered with partners in the mAKE consortium on how to continually disseminate the passport prototype and learn from peoples' experiences with it. The table below sets out the activities, outputs and initial outcomes, as at the end of Y2, in respect of creation and testing of the PSS and of the Maker Passport prototype.

WP4 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Future means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
<p>Developing mutual recognition open standard (People and Skills Specification (PSS)) and Maker Passport for the mutual recognition of makers' skills</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <p>Deliverable D4.1: Skills – Mutual Recognition Standard (People and Skills Specification (PSS))</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desktop research, 25 interviews, workshop at AMG in Cape Town, and collection of 96 responses to survey (conducted in collaboration with WP1 and WP6) • Creation of a PSS Working Group and regular meetings • Co-creation of initial open standard (PSS) for beta-testing (deliverable D4.1 of M12) <p>Deliverable D4.2: Skills – Maker Passport and Prototype</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-creation of first prototype of PSS-based Maker Passport system (M18) (sign-up form) • Internal and external promotion of standard via blog post, webinar, interview videos, IMA showcase webinar, flyer, and conference participation • 9 makerspaces from the Innovative Manufacturing in Africa (IMA) project use PSS/Passport system • 45 makers sign up for PSS/Passport • Video recordings posted to YouTube from the IMA showcase webinar and from IOP Community Calls on PSS work <p>The final prototype (D4.3) is due near the end of Y3 (M34, Dec. 2024).</p> <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback from the initial group of PSS/Passport registrants led to simplification of the registration form. • The simplified form generated numerous additional PSS/Passport registrations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal reports and documentation by consortium members involved in the task • Access and social media statistics for the Maker Passport system • FGDs with makers and DIHs/makerspaces who used the Maker Passport, so as to learn about the applicability and usage in different contexts and the benefits of usage • Interviews or an FGD with DIHs/makerspaces who did not follow up on use of the PSS/Maker Passport system, so as to learn from their experiences

6.1.4 First lessons learnt

WP4 conducted interviews with representatives of the nine IMA makerspaces who participated in testing the Maker Passport project, and sent out a questionnaire to the first group of 28 makers who signed up to the Passport. From this preliminary feedback, we learnt that the following two main changes were needed:

- The form for creating a new user record for a Maker Passport, using PSS, needed to be shortened, i.e., to have far fewer questions. (After shortening the form, we quickly received 17 new applications.)
- To reach a broader audience of makers (e.g., when engaging in a call for bids to produce an item), it would be helpful for the Maker Passport form to be available via a mobile app such as WhatsForm. (This lesson learnt will be taken into account in the further development work in Y3.)

People and Skills Sign Up

Name (Last, First)

Email

Birthdate

This question is necessary in case there is any legal safety requirement (to be over the age of 18) to use space or equipment.

With which makerspace are you currently affiliated?

List any makerspaces, labs, or other workspace(s) you currently work in, or have a membership.

Do you currently belong to any maker networks, artisan guilds, or other related consortia? If yes, please list. If no, enter 'N/A':

Please share any certifications and/or trainings that you have completed or received related to your work in makerspaces or fablabs. This could be anything from basic safety, to using specific equipment, or apprenticing in a certain craft or skill like wood turning or 3D modeling.

Anything additional you would like to share about your work

[Submit on WhatsApp](#)

A WhatsApp form created using [WhatsForm](#)

A simplified form was created using WhatsForm and shared with the IMA cohort as well, receiving positive response.

https://whatsform.com/Q_oQU0

Having the maker passport prototype form embedded directly into a mobile app allows for simple distribution, ease of use by participants, and simplified analysis of results via a consolidated dashboard.

Whether using WhatsForm or another mobile integration service for surveys, investment in hosting the survey or hiring a third part support vendor will need to be made to manage the data collection and analysis.

Figure 4: Maker Passport – simplified record form for users

6.1.5 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3

Key activities in Y3 will include:

- Designing a second Maker Passport prototype and testing it
- Roll-out of the prototypes to additional makerspaces and makers
- Monthly PSS Working Group meetings to steer the process and lay the foundations for sustainability (which will stem from an active community that has ownership of the initiative and the prototypes produced)
- Activities to gather feedback on the prototypes
- A communication campaign, including social media elements as well as recorded webinars and/or conference presentations, e.g., AOSH and IOP Community Calls, GiG-related events, Fab City and

Fab Conference programming, Nation of Makers and Open Source Hardware Association (OSHWAA) programming

During the PSS Working Group monthly meetings,⁹ the roadmap for iteration of the first prototype (i.e., the survey) and for development of another prototype to test were discussed and agreed upon, based on opportunity and capacity of the community, as well as potential partners to collaborate with. Partners to collaborate with will be instrumental, as we are working with prototypes that aim at gathering a combination of proof-of-concept and proof-of-value of the PSS/Passport prototype. The consequence of this is that we rely on partners willing to spend time to explore first prototypes and their iterations, as well as take the time to provide feedback.

Grounded in the Y3 activities listed above, evaluation and impact assessment data collection will include some or all of the following:

- An FGD, or individual interviews, with additional makerspaces and makers to collect formative feedback on perceived usefulness and applicability of the PSS/Maker Passport prototype(s) rolled out during Y3
- Impact interviews with selected makerspaces probing the future potential value of the PSS/Maker Passport
- An FGD, or individual interviews, with makerspaces who did not follow up on using the PSS/Maker Passport
- Access statistics and social media statistics
 - WP5 access to social media statistics on communication campaign
 - Conference registration/participation numbers

6.2 Map of Machinery

The objective of WP4's Map of Machinery initiative is to facilitate distributed manufacturing by aggregating and visualising machine-availability data provided by makers, innovation organisations, and distributed manufacturing entities. A core aim is to create an open and reliable information source for locating both digital and traditional manufacturing capabilities. The machinery in question produces a diverse range of items –everything from wooden chairs to biotech devices used in laboratories.

The mAKE project's Map of Machinery has its origins in the work conducted by the IOP between 2020–2022 on a mapping data standard for documenting and sharing information, on a global basis, about the location of manufacturing facilities and capabilities in or near makerspaces. The standard was published in 2021 as the "Open Know-Where", or "OKW", data standard.

⁹ See <https://community.internetofproduction.org/c/initiatives-channel/people-skills/>

Figure 5: Map at <https://map.internetofproduction.org/makeafricaeu.html>

WP4 conducted workshops and training to disseminate information on the Map of Machinery, its use cases, and the current tools for contribution to the dataset. Notably, the Africa Open Science Hardware (AOSH) sessions organised by MboaLab in late 2022 were instrumental. Direct interviews were conducted with representatives of DIHs/makerspaces, innovation organisations, and distributed manufacturing entities during events including re:publica and GiG sessions in Berlin (June 2023). Questions focused on exploration of makers' collaborative efforts and methodologies for finding potential maker resources, such as other actors, infrastructure, machinery, and collaborative projects. The qualitative data collected informed the initial design of Map-of-Machinery data collection forms deployed on platforms including Airtable and KoboToolbox.

WP4 commenced with an initial pool of 23 organisations, who were guided on sharing of machine-inventory information and locations, and other metadata necessary for the mapping of machines and their capabilities. Later, the directory increased through the contributions of mAKE consortium partners and their networks, totalling 53 until at the time of finalising this report at the end of Y2 (January 2024).

Between May and September 2023, three distinct data collection exercises were executed. The initial exercise covered 49 makerspace locations in Africa and four in Europe, resulting in the receipt and parsing of 21 inventories into machines, materials, and tools.

The second exercise was a collaboration with the [OKW Manufacturing World Map Data Awards](#), a programme funded by the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation that supports volunteer or academic teams to conduct data collection in their communities. Through this programme, the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Uganda team expanded on work conducted in 2020–2021 (the first experiment in using the OKW data standard to map machinery locations), and, in 2023, the award supported OKW data collection in Greece (27 locations) and Nigeria (59 locations). The 2023 OKW data was collected from a diverse range of entities, from small traditional manufacturers to digital manufacturing hubs (e.g., makerspaces, fab labs, university labs).

The third exercise was a collaboration with the aforementioned IMA project. The nine IMA project makerspaces participated in testing the data entry forms for the Map of Machinery, providing direct feedback (during individual meetings with IMA project management and monthly meetings involving all nine IMA makerspaces) on useability, and sharing their processes and formats for inventorying machines. The IMA makerspaces and their machines now feature on the Internet of Production's worldwide [OKW Map of Manufacturing](#). Utilising the collected inventory information, a repository of technical specifications for 3D printers and CNC machines¹⁰ was developed. This informed the redesign of the inventory form, simplifying technical information submission requirements for contributors and enhancing data analysis for reporting purposes. The data collection tool KoboToolbox emerged as the most valuable due to its offline functionality, cost-effectiveness, and well-documented form-design process.³ Currently hosted on a server maintained by the UNHCR (UN Refugee Agency), the system ensures regular maintenance and high data availability.

In addition to three direct data collection efforts just outlined, data compilation from existing networks, including [Fablabs.io](#), [Make Works](#), and [Verbund Offener Werkstätten](#), contributed 2.664 additional entries from Europe and Africa.⁴ The aggregated data underwent processing and homogenisation for the mapping exercise. (Challenges in data analysis are addressed in section 6.2.1 below.)

The gathered information demonstrated the diverse types of available data and underscored the impact of the selected tools on data collection, consistency (quality), time processing, and map visualisation. Initially, some tools used proved unstable for continuous self-hosting services, leading to resource-intensive maintenance. This prompted a shift towards more reliable and simplified tools. While the development priority primarily centres on design for usability rather than the software infrastructure, detailed information about the governance shift is covered in section 6.2.1.

¹⁰ See Anaya Herndandez, A. (2023). IOP-Alliance / okw_machines_catalog. GitHub. https://github.com/iop-alliance/okw_machines_catalog. This repository provides datasets for the most common machine brands and models found at makerspaces and fab labs via the IOP Alliance OKW initiative.

DATA SUBMISSION

Figure 6: Data collection tool at <https://map.internetofproduction.org/data-submission/index.html>

WP4 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Future means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
<p>Map of Machinery documenting machines in and near DIHs/makerspaces across Africa and Europe</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Map of Machinery entries from Europe and Africa: https://map.internetofproduction.org/makeafricaeu.html ● Collection of data aligned to Open Know-Where (OKW) standard ● Publishing of existing data ● Creation and testing of data upload processes, supported by a blogpost and an email shared among consortium members ● Machinery data integrated into existing maps via an API ● Creation of open datasets: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Repository of technical specifications for 3D printers and CNC machines ● Based on the collection and count programme, the location entries from published sources were: “Europe”: 1.580; “Africa”: 93; “Oceania”: 19; “Asia”: 416; and “Americas”: 556. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Internal reports and documentation by consortium members involved in the task ● Online access statistics (access to the Map of Machinery, the surveys and the Git repositories) and social media statistics ● Notes and video recordings from OKW Working Group meetings ● Impact-pathway interviews with makerspaces that have used the Map of Machinery ● Case study/user story data collection from makerspaces that have used the Map of Machinery

WP4 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Future means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From the OKW Data Awards and other related surveys: “Africa”: 8.327; “Asia”: 1.171; “Europe”: 15. (https://github.com/iop-alliance/okw_data_management/blob/main/data_count.ipynb) • Identification of stories about the usage of the map to initiate further improvements via the internal report on the IMA project. <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback from makerspaces led to redesign of the inventory form for the Map of Machinery • The 3 direct data collection exercises generated recruitment of new members to the OKW community, which enabled the revival of the OKW Working Group in January 2024 • The OKW Data Awards, leveraging the OKW standard and the Map of Machinery surveying tools, enabled academic and civil society groups in Greece and Nigeria to gather data to support their academic and social outcomes 	

The currently publicly available datasets are held in Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/communities/iopa>, as CSV file outputs using the Python programs available at okw-data-management repositories. A selection of tables is on constant update and the latest version is to be published after validation of compliance with the EU’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). A data policy, following the official GDPR checklist tool, has been written and is also under review and available publicly at <https://map.internetofproduction.org/data-privacy-policy/index.html>.

6.2.1 First lessons learnt

Several lessons have been gleaned from the initial phases of the machinery-mapping initiative. Challenges include linking to existing inventory lists, avoiding data duplication, ensuring data currency, simplifying upload processes, and maintaining data quality. A combination of manual and automated processes is currently employed to reconcile data from different sources, to detect duplicates, to address irrelevancies, to update outdated data, and to complete missing data. A data management repository has been implemented, housing Python programs and criteria governing data inclusion/exclusion during collection processes.

Open-Know-Where

World manufacturing map, DevOps infrastructure
Rev.0 March 16 2023

Author: Antonio de Jesus Anaya Hernandez, DevOps Eng.
Author: The Internet of Production Alliance, 2023
<https://internetofproduction.org>
This work is licensed under [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)

Figure 7: Open-Know-Where DevOps infrastructure diagram (Rev.0)

The need for automation of data cleanse and analysis by the OKW initiative was emphasised, particularly when collecting databases from makers and distributed manufacturing networks, given the larger volume of data (in the order of thousands) compared to surveying tools (in the order of tens). Otherwise the data would have to be processed manually, thus increasing development times. Notably, surveying conducted by organisations with strong community bounds, and person-to-person interactions, have so far proven more effective, in terms of participation and data accumulation, than online-only surveys

Independence from paid data platforms has been achieved through the adoption of KoboToolbox, a surveying tool which offers many advantages when used in areas with low internet coverage, and GitHub repositories, platform for keeping versions and track of contributions seamlessly, and widely use in the maintenance of software tools from hobbyist to industrial solutions. The transition from Airtable Forms and DigitalOcean hosting to KoboToolbox and GitHub pages has been instrumental to achievement of a platform-agnostic knowledge source.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016858.

Ensuring data privacy and compliance with GDPR regulations has presented challenges, necessitating defined and disclosed processes and data sources. The current collection processes include a public-view map and a research-access-only data repository, with GDPR compliance considerations dictating the temporary classification of certain information as "only for research".

Distinguishing between database formation, data visualisation, and data aggregation is crucial for designing effective processes and infrastructure, for an usable toolset that prioritises the collection of manufacturing locations and their inventory information in a comprehensible way, with the objective of enabling distributed manufacturing across various makers use cases in Africa and in compliance with data privacy regulators like GDPR. Examples of use cases are:

- Makers at all levels seeking communities and resources for their projects.
- Organisations searching for capable makerspaces or traditional manufacturing workshops in third countries. This is especially relevant for those planning to implement humanitarian projects with open-source hardware components, such as water filtration or desalination, using projects like the [LibreWater](#) project.
- Professionals specialising in horizontal learning, seeking open education programmes such as the [Fab Academy](#), or engaging in short workshops to develop both soft and hard skills, including areas such as carpentry and design thinking, among others.

Community involvement in defining requirements and evaluating proposed solutions has triggered a governance shift in technical development. This transition shifts from board-based decision-making to proposing solutions based on collected data and direct feedback from African field experts, emphasising a first-hand, user-centric vision of data usability and the subsequent tools developed for it, such as the Map of Machinery, the catalogue of machines, and the notebooks transparently holding data acquisition processes.

The extended development time for the data system highlights the significance of a robust software technical requirements process. This process is set to prioritise components and functionalities to swiftly address and solve on-field problems. Initially, the priority was the visualisation of data, leading to modifications in the data structure. The technical requirements for data services needed for deployment, such as SQL or NoSQL databases, data output files, and cartography map hosting services, were adjusted to align with user experience considerations.

More work is needed on defining the data governance and its in progress being solved on every tool release and across partnership talks, events, and meetings.

Links to resources discussed above:

- [OKW standard](#)
- [OKW machines catalogue](#)

- [OKW data management](#)
- [OKW Data Awards Cohort 2](#)
- [OKW data collection tool](#)
- [KoboToolbox](#)
- [FabLabs.io](#), [MakeWorks](#), [Verbund Offene Werkstaetten](#)

6.2.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3

The following activities, which include evaluation and impact assessment data collection, will be conducted in Y3:

Collection of access and social media statistics

- Tool Implementation: Implement robust analytics tools to track user behaviour on the machinery-mapping platform.
- Social media strategy:
 - Enhance the social media strategy to increase visibility and engagement.
 - Leverage targeted campaigns to reach specific user groups.

Workshops with makerspaces and networks

(including Fab conference in Puebla, Mexico, 4–9 August 2024):

Diversified workshop content:

- Diversify workshop content to address specific needs of different makerspaces and networks.
- Offer advanced sessions for experienced users and introductory sessions for newcomers.

Interactive elements:

This will primarily be conducted within the OKW Working Group, as well as during IOP Community Calls. It covers:

- Include interactive elements such as Q&A sessions and collaborative problem-solving activities.
- Encourage active participation and knowledge-sharing among attendees.

Impact assessment with DIHs/makerspaces

Case study/user stories approach:

- Select a relevant sample of DIHs/makerspaces.
- Explore their journey with the Map of Machinery, emphasising challenges, successes, and lessons learnt.

User engagement initiatives

- Implement targeted user engagement initiatives, such as webinars, to maintain interest and participation.
- Encourage user-generated content, such as success stories or best practices.

Reporting and documentation

- Comprehensive reporting:
 - Compile a comprehensive report consolidating findings from access statistics, workshops, and impact interviews. This will be in the deliverable D4.3: Machinery – Map, to be completed in November 2024 (M34).
 - Include visualisations to enhance data presentation.
- Actionable recommendations:
 - Provide actionable recommendations based on the assessment results for further enhancements and optimisations.

6.3 Digital contracting system for distributed manufacturing

WP4's prototype digital contracting system for distributed manufacturing aims to enable contracting of decentralised work to several DIHs/makerspaces, such that the DIHs/makerspaces can be contracted to perform manufacturing functions for a single purchase order. The contracting prototype aims, among other things, to enable (through building in quality assurance steps) contractor trust in a process through which a contract is fulfilled by several small-scale manufacturers in diverse locations rather than by a single, larger manufacturer.

For WP4's work on the digital contracting system for distributed manufacturing, 2023 (Y2) was a year of information-gathering. In collaboration with the nine aforementioned IMA project makerspaces (in Ghana, Kenya, and South Africa), who functioned as a sample of diverse African DIHs/makerspaces, we collected stakeholder requirements for the contracting system. Our approach, rather than a traditional interview or FGD discussion approach, was to run a trial of what the system should enable, without the system existing. All steps the system should enable were undertaken by personnel at the nine IMA makerspaces, who were then able to provide insights on needs, challenges and requirements for such a system.

The trial consisted of three rounds of localised manufacturing of identical items by makerspaces in each of the three IMA project countries (Ghana, Kenya, South Africa) through inviting the community of nine makerspaces to respond to the offer. The spaces were required to publish the request for quotations, to select the manufacturers (makers) and contract with them, to ensure the actual manufacturing to place, to perform quality checks, to deliver the manufactured product point of need (in this case, local health facilities), and to pay the manufacturers (the local makers).

The feedback from the nine makerspaces who participated in the requirement–elicitation trial exercise was collected via:

- Monthly check-in meetings during the trial (from August to November 2023).
- Discussions at an online showcase event during which the makerspaces presented their achievements and challenges.
- Discussions between the project manager of the trial and the makerspace leaders.
- Interviews by the trial project manager with some of the makers and makerspaces who conducted the trial.

WP4 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Future means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
<p>Digital contracting system to distribute production across the DIHs/makerspaces network</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A model contract document enabling contracting of a distributed set of makers by one customer • Assessment and contract allocation matrix • Testing of a distributed production of 3 items across 3 countries with 9 makerspaces to inform the requirements for a digital contracting system for distributed manufacturing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Test 1: 18 participants Test 2: 12 participants Test 3: 13 participants • Interviews with 3 of the makers and 3 of the makerspaces who tested the contracting system, final IMA report, and IMA showcase webinar. <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The contracting trial alerted us to the need to pay careful attention to the diversity of roles required in such a system • The contracting trial reinforced the centrality of trust to the success of such a system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal reports and documentation by consortium members involved in the task • Pre-test of the digital contract: lessons learnt and notes from the tests • Testimonies from participating makerspaces • Online access statistics for the prototype, and social media statistics for the communication activities

6.3.1 First lessons learnt

The trial of the contracting system enabled us to see emerging processes and requirements for a distributed/decentralised manufacturing system, particularly one that provides a contract mechanism that links to the Map of Machinery and the Maker Passport and is based on the business models catalogue developed in WP1, specifically the “manufacturing as a service” and “quality control” business models. As a key starting point for the development of the system, we gained a sense of the different roles that may

need to be considered. The trial has confirmed that there are many actors and components in the process, including:

- Demand-side roles: payer, recipient, user of the product.
- Intermediary roles: quality controller, logistics person, matcher of supply and demand.
- supply-side roles: designer, manufacturer.

These findings on roles resonate with elements set out in this [2022 IOP article in Medium](#).

The trial also reinforced the importance of trust to the success of the contracting system: trust in the manufacturer; trust in the quality of the products; and before all that, trust in the customer (i.e., trust that the payment will come, and that the order is real).

Feedback from trial participants indicated that the trial has successfully demonstrated the value of a system that enables DIHs/makerspaces to play mediating roles in provision of manufacturing business opportunities to their communities. This feedback came in different ways from the makerspaces who participated in the trial. The makerspace leaders found that they were able to successfully serve as communication conduits; as quality warranters (and capacity builders in this regard); as market opportunity analysts and providers; and as payment agents.

6.3.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3

In 2024, the work on developing the digital contracting system is to be organised as follows:

1. Write the technical specifications for a refined digital contracting system.
2. Prototype this system.
3. Test the system

Building on the Y2 learnings, the key steps in WP3, including steps aimed at generating qualitative evaluation and impact assessment data, will be:

- Conducting expert interviews with at least five members of the IOP ecosystem to inform the writing of the technical specifications of the system.
- Creating a stakeholder map/list that identifies the variety of user types and lists potential partners—via interviews and, if necessary, after completion of the interviews, a workshop.
- Developing a prototype and implementing a technical test plan with one user and then several users. The test plan will include collecting feedback from testers via interviews and/or survey forms.
- Evaluating the system to assess its perceived usefulness and applicability—via interviewing of makerspaces testing the system.

- Communications: Presenting the prototype in at least one webinar and one community event; creating information materials; and documenting the prototype to enable further uses and participation from the mAKE/IOP community.

Quantitative evaluation will be based on online access statistics for the prototype, and social media statistics for the communication activities.

7. Communication, dissemination and outreach (WP5)

WP5 is dedicated to the communication and dissemination of project outputs and findings to defined target audiences in the best communicable form. The aim of the outreach activities is to maximise project impact and support the project's capacity building, community engagement and network-building, providing key stakeholders with the necessary information in a time-effective manner that allows for early engagement, market uptake, and implementation. The communication and dissemination work of the mAKE project has, as of January 2024 (last month of Y2), generated the following outputs and initial outcomes:

WP5 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Future means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
<p>Develop and establish a dissemination and outreach campaign</p> <p>Create project identity, website and social media</p> <p>Define and develop guidelines for capacity building tools for social innovation</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable D5.1: Communication, Dissemination and Outreach (CDO) Plan (M3) • Clear and recognisable visual identity (M3) • Guidelines, templates and how-tos for best practices for designing project outputs and self-learning tools (M12) <p>Website</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12.762 total page views <p>Online/offline events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 50 events in which mAKE participated • 73.595 participants in mAKE-related events <p>Social media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 54.851 views across all social media channels • 339 posts on social media • 942 followers across all social media (275 on Instagram, 222 on Twitter, 61 on Facebook, 384 on LinkedIn) • 20 videos shared on YouTube <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation on event promotion between WP5 and WP6, and between these two WPs and WPs 1-4, has 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal reports and documentation by mAKE consortium members involved in the task • Google Analytics web statistics on mAKE website • Access and social media statistics for mAKE online communication tools • Feedback from mAKE members and the DIH/makerspace network (documented in the "events collector" spreadsheet)

WP5 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Future means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
	<p>generated increasingly strong website and social media statistics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of mAKE among the project's stakeholder groups has grown through the project's aggressive use of social media and the project's participation in numerous events • Mutual learning and experience-sharing, between the mAKE consortium and the project's stakeholders, has been facilitated through the numerous webinars produced in collaboration with WP6 and other WPs 	

7.1 First lessons learnt

We learnt that collaborative communication planning, and frequent internal sharing of elements of the communication plan within the consortium, are key for ensuring all members of the consortium are involved and committed to the best results. To this end, we found that monthly online meetings helped maintain focus on how each project activity should be communicated and promoted. Also, regular contact with communication partners in other projects in the "ICT-58 family" of EU Horizon 2020 projects has enhanced collaboration and sustainability of the communication activities. Another valuable learning has been that, in certain purposes, online events can perform as well as, or even better than, offline events.

7.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3

The evaluation of WP5 activities will continue via Google Analytics and the statistics of our social media channels, as well as the internal reporting tools (e.g., internal "events collector") that help to collect data on all the dissemination and communication activities conducted by the consortium members in their networks. There will also be continued probing and documentation of lessons learnt.

8. Community engagement and sustainability (WP6)

WP6, led in the mAKE consortium by GiG, is dedicated to active community engagement, ensuring that the mAKE stakeholder communities are involved in the co-creation of mAKE outputs. The WP aims to meet the real needs of target communities and support bottom-up development of sustainable knowledge and infrastructure. The activities of WP6 link closely to WP5's dissemination and communication work, and to all the content creation and digital infrastructure development in WPs 1 to 4. The key engaged actors of this work package are the makers, technology developers, startups, SMEs, DIHs/makerspaces and leaders of

DIHs/makerspaces, many of whom are part of the mAKE consortium members' networks. These actors have all been actively engaged in the co-development of mAKE outputs and outcomes. Overall, there was a 28% increase in Y2, over Y1, in terms of community engagement numbers.

WP6 worked closely with WP2's lead consortium entity, the AMN, on AMN's hosting of its annual Africa Makerspace Gathering (AMG) in Cape Town near the end of Y1 (November 2022). This AMG featured several mAKE knowledge co-creation sessions, including sessions focused on co-creation between core mAKE consortium representatives and DIH/makerspace community members in attendance. The knowledge co-creation fed, among other things, into development of WP1 and WP4 deliverables executed in Y2 (see Chapters 3 and 6 above).

In support of WP1's Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM), GIG, in Y2 WP6 co-hosted numerous WP6-WP1 community discussion webinars, with a focus on community inputs for, awareness of, and engagement with, the OCBM. There have been six such discussion webinars, covering edutainment, consultancy, working with artisans, manufacturing networks, membership models, and a presentation of the OCBM deliverable (which allowed for feedback and peer review). More than 2.700 community members engaged through these webinars, with the strongest European engagement in Germany and Spain and the strongest African engagement in Ghana, Kenya, Egypt, and Cameroon. These community discussions will continue in Y3, with an emphasis on global perspectives.

Also, as part of the consortium's knowledge creation and sharing, five webinars were prepared and presented during the consortium's monthly online meetings, with the webinars featuring Fab City, the Critical Making project, IAAC, GIG, and the IOP Alliance. The recordings of these webinars, branded as "Knowledge Pills", have been disseminated through consortium members' networks and embedded into the dedicated mAKE YouTube channel linked to the mAKE website. More than 200 community members have been engaged through these Knowledge Pills.

WP6 collaborated with WP1 (and WP5 on communication materials) for the May 2023 launch of the first iteration of the aforementioned Makers-in-Residency (MiR) programme (see Chapter 3 on WP1), alongside promotion of the five-person Stakeholder Jury established at the same time. (The Stakeholder Jury is supporting two WP1 programmes: the MiR programme and the Venture Building and Business Development programme.) More than 60 MiR applications from across Europe and Africa were received and the call for participation was disseminated through each consortium member's network as well as through mAKE online channels. mAKE consortium member AMN was the predominant community network from which applicants were received, followed by applications from AfricaOSH and GIG members, as well as approximately 30 non-affiliated applicants (suggesting the need for future focus, in the consortium, on community engagement that sparks activation of network membership by unaffiliated DIHs/makerspaces).

In addition to its collaboration with WP1 establishing the MiR programme and Stakeholder Jury, and with WP5 on all promotion and communication activities related to the MiR and the Stakeholder Jury, WP6 facilitated training of selected MiR participants in use of Wikifactory documentation (for longevity, as part of the sharing and embedding strategy). WP6 also collaborated with WP1 on development of the second MiR round (MiR 2.0), which was launched in November 2023, this time in collaboration with the Vulca network of European makerspaces.

The central goal of the mAKE project is to create a shared understanding of the explicit, implicit, tacit, and procedural knowledge necessary for individual makers to participate in and easily navigate a distributed manufacturing ecosystem. To that end, 14 resources have, to date, been embedded in the online assets of the mAKE project and its consortium members—including, for example, the IOP Alliance’s Map of Machinery developed under WP. The Map has been embedded in both the mAKE and GIG websites, and is available, through the IOP Alliance website, for other networks and communities who decide to do the same.

In June 2023, during the re:publica event in Berlin, GIG, on behalf of mAKE, hosted a panel discussion on activating networks and the value of communities. This panel included a representative of the Hubiquitous project, which, like mAKE, is part of the “ICT-58 family” of EU Horizon 2020 projects. In September 2023, a mAKE representative visited ICT-58 member ENRICH in Africa’s sustainability centre in Cape Town, in order to share best practices and gain insights into sustainability strategies and outcomes.

WP6 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Future means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
<p>Manage the community</p> <p>Facilitate and support results sharing and embedding</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deliverable D6.1: Community Activation & Engagement Strategy (M12): ● Deliverable D6.3: Sharing & Embedding Strategy (M12): Guidelines for open sharing and knowledge communing, describing how all members can embed the mAKE outputs into their portfolios ● 73.500+ engagements from the mAKE community ● 51 events organised ● 11 WP6 webinars produced, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 6 community discussions, with 2.700+ engagements from the mAKE community ● 5 Knowledge Pills recorded, with 200+ engagements from the mAKE community ● 14 resources embedded ● 10 sharing activities for collaboration and learning (with ICT-58 family of Horizon 2020 projects) ● Collaboration with WP1 on launch of 2 community programmes: MiR 1.0, MiR 2.0 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Internal reports and documentation by consortium members involved in the task ● Access and social media statistics of mAKE communication tools ● Feedback from mAKE members on the usefulness of engagement strategy, guidelines and code of conduct. ● Updating living documents eg. co-creation reporting. ● Stories about the quality of communicated engagement by mAKE stakeholders

WP6 planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y2	Future means of evaluation data gathering in Y3
	<p>Initial outcomes: Strong mutual learning and experience-sharing between WP6 and other WPs, e.g.,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● With WP1, via collaboration on the OCBM, MiR and Venture Building and Business Development programmes ● With WP5, via collaboration on community discussion webinars, Knowledge Pills, and communications related to key deliverables (e.g., MiR, Stakeholder Jury) ● Awareness of mAKE among the project's stakeholder groups has grown through the project's aggressive use of numerous activation and engagement methods. ● Mutual learning and experience-sharing, between the mAKE consortium and the project's stakeholders, has been facilitated through the activation and engagement activities ● mAKE collaboration with the Vulca network, enabled by Vulca's membership WP lead entity GIG, has greatly strengthened mAKE's ability to deliver the MiR programme (i.e., MiR 2.0) 	

8.1 First lessons learnt

We found that certain mAKE programmes—for example, WP1's MiR programme—were struggling to generate strong participation by European DIHs/makerspaces. Accordingly, we reached out to the GIG-member European maker network, Vulca, to get assistance with ensuring engagement with, and activation of, European makers and makerspaces in the context of mAKE offerings.

Another key learning was the hindrances created, particularly for the MiR programme, by the challenges African nationals face in acquiring visas in their respective African countries in order to travel to Europe (see Chapter 3). In order to combat this, when selecting participants for future programmes where travel to Europe is required, embassy alignment will be heavily investigated and accounted for in the final planning and execution, with an additional four-month preparation time incorporated so as to ensure adequate time for securing visa appointments and visa processing.

8.2 Further evaluation and impact assessment in Y3

The evaluation of WP6 activities will be conducted via the collection of quantitative indicators and qualitative lessons learnt, as contributed and shared by the involved consortium members. In addition, stories about the quality of mAKE communication and engagement will be collected from external stakeholders in order to generate additional qualitative data.

9. Overview of mAKE indicator framework at end of Y2 and summary of lessons learnt

The table below provides indicators (at micro, meso and macro levels) for: key outputs up to the end of Y2; initial outcomes up to the end of Y2; as well as indicators for the intermediate outcomes (end of Y3) and long-term outcomes (after Y3).

	Micro level (individual makers, innovators, etc.)	Meso level (makerspaces, DIHs, startups, etc.)	Macro level (associations, networks, policy level, etc.)
Key outputs (up to end of Y2)	<p>Individual participants actively involved in co-designing, shaping and using the mAKE outputs</p> <p>Makers-in-Residency (MiR) programme:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MiR 1.0: 66 makers applied, 4 selected • MiR 2.0: 45 makers applied, 16 shortlisted <p>mAKE open educational resources (OERs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online survey to collect OERs received 15 high-quality responses from external stakeholders • Open Makerspace Toolkit, comprising elements of approximately 80 existing OERs and 3 OERs created by the mAKE consortium, published on adaptable, open access web 	<p>DIHs/makerspaces, startups and SMEs and other relevant stakeholders actively involved in co-designing, shaping and using the mAKE outputs</p> <p>Venture building and business models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 companies selected for Venture Building programme (out of 53 who applied) • 1 general onboarding session, with 11 companies and 4 experts joining • 19 individual needs assessment sessions conducted • 50 successful DIHs/makerspaces interviewed for development of Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM) <p>mAKE policy agenda:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 11 FGDs and 7 interviews conducted to develop common policy agenda • total of 69 participants (26 from Africa, 43 from Europe) involved in the FGDs and interviews 	<p>Political decision-makers and representatives of DIH associations involved in co-designing, shaping, using the mAKE outputs</p> <p>mAKE events to discuss policy agenda and recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • community discussion webinar on common policy agenda draws 26 participants, including a local government representative, African and European experts, makers, and DIH/makerspace leaders <p>mAKE resources created and shared:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7 case studies of collective organisation and policy-related actions by DIH/makerspace associations created and shared • Recommendations for development of DIH/makerspace networks and associations created and shared

	<p>platform</p> <p>mAKE infrastructure developed and tested:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 96 responses to the survey that collected requirements for the PSS/Maker Passport system • Prototype of PSS/Maker Passport system developed (M18) • 45 makers sign up for the PSS/Maker Passport • Testing of a distributed production system (3 items across 3 countries) by individual makers: Test 1: 18 participants, Test 2: 12 participants, Test 3: 13 participants <p>mAKE events and social media:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 50 events in which mAKE participated • 6 community discussion webinars, with 2.700+ stakeholders engaged • 5 Knowledge Pill webinars, with 200+ stakeholders engaged • 54.851 views across all social media channels • 339 publications on social media • 942 followers across all social media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 community discussion webinar convened to receive inputs on components of draft policy agenda <p>mAKE networking events organised:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 founder-to-founder (F2F) matchmaking events • 1 business-to-business (B2B) networking event <p>mAKE business modelling and venture building resources created and shared:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 17 published business models, in Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM), for hardware-focused DIHs/makerspaces • 6 webinars linked to OCBM, with 2.700+ engagements from the mAKE community • 3 makerspaces (in Germany, Cameroon, Zimbabwe) involved in a mentoring programme using the OCBM <p>mAKE digital Infrastructure developed and tested:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 9 makerspaces (in Ghana, Kenya and South Africa) tested PSS/Maker Passport prototype • 9 makerspaces (in Ghana, Kenya and South Africa) tested inventory form for Map of Machinery • 9 makerspaces (and associated makers) tested digital contracting system for distributed manufacturing • Entries in the Map of Machinery: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Location entries from published sources: "Europe": 1.580; "Africa": 93; "Oceania": 19; "Asia": 416; "Americas": 556 ○ Location entries from OKW Data Awards and other related surveys: "Africa": 8.327; "Asia": 1.171; "Europe": 15 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common Policy Agenda and Recommendations for Policy Makers completed
--	--	---	--

<p>Initial outcomes (up to end of Y2)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Powerful networking, mutual-experience exchange, co-creation, awareness-raising, and learning at individual level amongst the engaged makers • Greatly improved engagement with European makers and makerspaces through collaboration with Vulca network • Improved upload processes for the PSS/Maker Passport system • Better understanding of processes and requirements for digital contracting system for distributed manufacturing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Powerful networking, mutual-experience exchange, co-creation, awareness-raising, and learning at a makerspace level • Good initial feedback on the OCBM: makerspaces and those supporting makerspaces use the information and perceive it as helpful • The Ukrainian Makers Association has translated the OCBM into Ukrainian, translations of the catalogue into French, Spanish, and Portuguese are in discussion • All 20 selected companies in the Venture Building programme have made a commitment to participate in post-programme impact-reporting • Feedback from makerspaces led to redesign of the inventory form for the Map of Machinery • The trial of the contracting system drew attention to the need to pay careful attention to the diversity of roles required in such a system. • The contracting trial reinforced the centrality of trust to the success of such a system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-depth mutual-experience exchange, co-creation, awareness-raising, and learning about policy requirements and recommendations • Stakeholder inputs at community discussion webinar on common policy agenda ensured that WP2 remains cognizant of the need to collaborate with local decision-makers and local institutions in policy formulation
<p>Intermediate outcomes (at end of Y3)</p>	<p>Capacity building and knowledge gains</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased knowledge amongst the key audiences on of how to set up, manage and equip DIHs and makerspaces (based on OERs and MOOC) • Mutual learning between involved makers and makerspaces of the makers-in-residency programme <p>Visibility gains and</p>	<p>Capacity building and knowledge gains</p> <p>Inspiration and increased practical knowledge about different successful business models for startups and makerspaces</p> <p>Increased knowledge of digital contracting systems</p> <p>Visibility gains and increased collaboration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased transparency and improved demonstration of Machinery available • Increased networking and mutual learning between founders and businesses 	<p>Capacity building and knowledge gains</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased knowledge of how to support DIHs in the different national contexts • Increased understanding of how to develop and trigger bottom-up DIH networks • Better understanding about the innovation potential of DIHs and makerspaces for local production <p>Dissemination/uptake of the policy recommendations in other international policy dialogues</p>

	<p>increased collaboration between makers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved demonstration of skills and experience levels of participating makers Facilitated search for peers to scale up production and fill skill gaps Facilitated search for mentors Increased collaboration between makers of all genders, age groups and social backgrounds <p>Engagement, awareness and motivation</p>	<p>Practical steps towards higher sustainability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 10 business models applied by local businesses SMEs/startups in the Venture Building programme able to make it to the next stage of venture building <p>Engagement, awareness and motivation</p> <p>Uptake, application and implementation of mAKE outputs by the DIH/makerspace community</p> <p>Sustainable embedding of mAKE outputs into consortium member portfolios</p>	<p>Mentions of the recommendations in regional policy documents</p> <p>Engagement, awareness and motivation</p> <p>Inclusion of more African members in DIH/makerspace networks</p>
<p>Long-term outcomes (after Y3)</p>	<p>A sustainable repository of open-source methods, devices and products used and implemented by members of DIHs/makerspaces</p> <p>Higher employability</p> <p>Increasing number of innovators</p> <p>Increasing number of co-created digital innovations</p>	<p>Opening business opportunities for African and European DIHs/makerspaces</p> <p>Increased revenue options for DIHs/makerspaces</p> <p>Sustainable usage of mAKE outputs</p> <p>New business alliances and more successful hardware startups and DIHs/makerspaces</p> <p>Scaling and replication of local production</p> <p>Raising uptake of distributed production</p>	<p>Changes in policies to support national and regional startup ecosystems</p> <p>Higher acceptance of DIHs/makerspaces by public authorities</p> <p>Better interfaces between the ecosystem players, including policy makers, DIHs/makerspaces, corporates and funders</p>

In addition to the indicators presented in the table above, the formative evaluation of project activities is providing a rich source of learning on how to best support DIHs/makerspaces and their work in Africa and Europe. For example, lessons have been learnt and documented on:

- The business models followed by successful DIHs/makerspaces and the ventures they host.
- The ways in which DIHs/makerspaces approach use of a business model catalogue.

- How to facilitate residencies by African makers at European DIHs/makerspaces.
- How to trigger matchmaking between makers/entrepreneurs, DIHs/makerspaces, and businesses.
- How DIH/makerspace associations engage with policy processes and policy makers.
- The wide range of OERs relevant to DIHs/makerspaces that are available for compilation into a dedicated toolkit.
- How maker skills can be documented and mutually recognised by DIHs/makerspaces, so as to facilitate skills portability.
- How machinery available in and near DIHs/makerspaces can be efficiently mapped online in support of distributed manufacturing.
- The roleplayers necessary for a successful digital contracting system for distributed manufacturing by makers, with DIHs/makerspaces serving as intermediaries.

While the mAKE consortium is still implementing many of the project outputs, including trainings, programmes and infrastructures for DIHs/makerspaces, we nevertheless already see compelling initial outcomes from the engagements with project stakeholders up to the end of Y2. The mAKE consortium has gained concrete insights, from the co-design processes, on how to better adapt the project outputs to the requirements and needs of DIHs/makerspaces. At the same time, the mAKE project's stakeholders have benefited from their involvement.

In WP1, for instance, the project's stakeholders have had access to the business model catalogue and have begun to determine how they can use it for their needs (e.g., getting inspired with respect to ways to finance activities they are planning to implement). In WP2, stakeholders were involved in mutual reflection and learning on the links between DIHs/makerspaces and policy matters. The resulting increased awareness of DIH/makerspace requirements when engaging with political decision makers and policy processes is a first step towards better future collaboration between stakeholders on policy matters—between DIHs/makerspaces, and between DIHs/makerspaces and policy actors. WP3 has drawn inputs from stakeholders on the kinds of OERs that need to be in the Open Makerspace Toolkit.

In WP4, there has been a strong engagement with stakeholders (makerspaces and makers in Africa) to better understand how distributed production processes can best be supported via digital innovations and infrastructures. WP5 and WP6 have been very strong in bringing the DIH/maker communities of Africa and Europe together and supporting mutual learning and sharing of experiences between them.

Within the consortium, a key overarching insight has been the need for flexibility in delivery of the WP activities. We are dealing with a great diversity of DIHs/makerspaces, with their diversity present with respect to, among other things, their activities, offerings, management structures, and financial and business models. And not only are the DIHs/makerspaces diverse, but also the makers themselves are very creative and dynamic people engaged in a diverse portfolio of activities and processes and often experiencing rapid changes in their employment situations. Thus, the resources, programmes and

infrastructures that mAKE develops require a high degree of flexibility—in, for example, duration and format—so as to be easily adaptable to the specific needs and requirements of our diverse stakeholders. However, at the same time, flexibility must also be accompanied by elements of centrally coordinated structure and guidance, so as to allow for the diverse people getting together and sharing their experiences and viewpoints to collaborate on, for example, the distributed production processes being tested in WP4.

In addition to the need for flexibility, the centrality of the issue of trust has also emerged as a key learning for the consortium. Trust is of paramount importance if, for example, DIHs/makerspaces and makers from Africa and Europe are to be able to successfully collaborate and learn from each other and then also reach out to other stakeholder groups based on successful collaborations. In WP1's MiR programme, the makerspace association Vulca has emerged as an important trusted interface between the mAKE consortium and European makers, with makerspaces preferring to be briefed by a known and trusted entity about projects and application procedures before submitting applications. In WP4's testing of digital contracting for distributed manufacturing, trust—in the skills of makers, in the quality of created products, in the reliability of involved producers and purchasers—has been identified as an important requirement. While the necessary trust can be fostered by previous relationships and working experiences, in the long run the developed infrastructures (for WP4's digital contract prototype for distributed manufacturing, and for other mAKE deliverables) should also support the generation of trust. In the case of distributed production processes, trusted makerspaces have the potential to become the intermediary entities that interface between purchasers and producers.

Another key learning has been the power of co-creation. There has been strong involvement of DIHs/makerspaces in the co-creation of WP4 infrastructures—for the PSS/Maker Passport, the Map of Machinery, and the digital contracting system for distributed manufacturing. This co-creation has been key to understanding the complex processes and entities involved in creating automated processes that successfully address challenges such as linking to existing inventory lists, avoiding data duplication, ensuring data currency, simplifying upload processes, and maintaining data quality.

The project's initial outcomes have also provided the consortium with frequent reminders of the importance of person-to-person interactions. When setting up the initial infrastructures necessary for key WP deliverables, strong community bonds—driven by consortium members' existing networks and animated, crucially, by person-to-person interactions—have been central to success. To give but one example, person-to-person interactions and face-to-face meetings have been crucial to the success of WP2's work to date towards a common policy agenda. And such interactions will continue to be of paramount importance to WP2 in Y3, as the WP works towards execution of its "Minister Meets Makers" programme.

10. Outlook

The main focus of the WP7 evaluation team in Y2 was on selection of evaluation instruments in collaboration with WP leaders, tailoring of the instruments to the WP requirements, and preparation for implementation of the instruments for evaluation data collection in Y3. This work was supported via regular calls with the WP leaders, using logic model matrices as the living documents for keeping track of all the activities, outputs, outcomes, indicators and evaluation instruments. Of course, the evaluation work is closely related to the WPs' timelines and milestones.

mAKE resources, programmes and digital infrastructures are being implemented in diverse regional and national contexts, and thus an in-depth understanding of the contexts in which outcomes can be realised is important. This aim will inform the evaluation team's use of quantitative and qualitative evaluation instruments. As evaluation data collection will be organised in various locations and with manifold mAKE consortium members, the evaluation team will provide mAKE members, when necessary, with the required briefings on use of the applicable evaluation instruments.

Pre-testing has been conducted for several of the key outputs—for example, the testing of the OCBM via the mentoring programme. Formative feedback and first indicators of initial outcomes have been collected, involving a wide range of stakeholders of the broader mAKEverse. This data collection for formative feedback and for indicators of outputs and outcomes will continue in Y3, while lessons learnt regarding expected long-term outcomes will have a certain time delay and will only come after the outputs have been fully applied, implemented, and used for a certain period of time.

While the evaluation data collection will be supported by all mAKE consortium members, the analysis and synchronisation of data will be conducted by the WP7 evaluation team, led and directed by ZSI, with the final results of this work presented in deliverables D7.3: Final Impact Assessment Report (M36) and D7.4: Impact Assessment Package.

References

- Anaya Herndandez, A. (2023). IOP-Alliance / okw_machines_catalog. GitHub. https://github.com/iop-alliance/okw_machines_catalog
- Kurz, B., & Kubek, D. (2016). *Social impact navigator: The practical guide for organizations targeting better results*. PHINEO gAG, Berlin. https://www.phineo.org/uploads/Downloads/PHINEO_Social_Impact_Navigator.pdf
- Mayring, P. (2000). Qualitative content analysis. *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-1.2.1089>
- Mayring, P. (2002). *Einführung in die qualitative Sozialforschung*. 5. Auflage. Weinheim, Basel.
- Morgan, D. (1997). Focus groups as a qualitative method. In *Focus groups as qualitative research* (2nd ed.) (pp. 8–17). SAGE. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781412984287>
- Peer 2 Peer University & The Mozilla Foundation (n.d.). An open badge system framework. Paper drafted in collaboration with The MacArthur Foundation, <http://bit.ly/badgепaper4>
- Witzel, A. (2000). The problem-centered interview. *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 1(1), 1438–5627. <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-1.1.1132>
- Woodyatt, C. R., Finneran, C. A., & Stephenson, R. (2016). In-person versus online focus group discussions: A comparative analysis of data quality. *Qualitative Health Research*, 26(6), 741–749. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732316631510>

